

GALLIUM-68 RADIOPHARMACY IN NUCLEAR MEDICINE

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Abstract. Gallium-68 (^{68}Ga) is a positron-emitting radionuclide that has gained prominence in nuclear medicine due to its exceptional versatility in diagnostic imaging and theranostics. Its unique physical and chemical properties make it ideal for PET imaging, especially in cancer diagnostics. This article provides an overview of ^{68}Ga 's role in radiopharmacy, explores its production methods and highlights its theranostic applications.

Keywords: Gallium-68, Nuclear medicine, Cyclotron production, Generator production $\text{Ge}^{68}/\text{Ga}^{68}$, Cancer diagnostics, Theranostics.

Introduction

Positron Emission Tomography (PET) has become an essential tool in medical imaging, providing valuable insights into the body's internal processes and aiding in the detection and monitoring of diseases, particularly in oncology, neurology and cardiology [1]. One of the most commonly used radionuclides in PET is Gallium-68 (^{68}Ga), known for its favorable imaging properties. ^{68}Ga has a short half-life of 68 minutes, making it ideal for clinical use. It can be easily incorporated into various radiopharmaceuticals, allowing for targeted imaging of specific biological processes [2]. Gallium-68 predominantly decays via positron emission, which accounts for approximately 89% of its total decay process. The emitted positrons have a maximum energy of 1.92 MeV. The remaining 11% of the decay occurs through electron capture, resulting in the formation of the stable isotope zinc-68 (^{68}Zn) [3].

Production

Gallium-68 (^{68}Ga) is primarily produced using two methods: cyclotron-based production and generator-based production. The most common method for obtaining Gallium-68 is through the $^{68}\text{Ge}/^{68}\text{Ga}$ parent/daughter radionuclide generator. Fig-1. In this process, the parent isotope Germanium-68 (^{68}Ge) is produced by irradiating natural gallium (^{69}Ga) with protons in a cyclotron, resulting in the $^{69}\text{Ga}(p,2n)^{68}\text{Ge}$ reaction. ^{68}Ge has a half-life of 270.95 days and decays to ^{68}Ga , which is then extracted from the generator using a saline solution [4, 5]. This method provides a reliable and on-demand source of ^{68}Ga , making it a

widely used approach in both clinical and research settings for producing radiopharmaceuticals. The $^{68}\text{Ge}/^{68}\text{Ga}$ generator is especially advantageous in settings where cyclotron facilities are not available, offering a cost-effective and accessible means of producing ^{68}Ga for PET imaging.[6]

Figure 1. Typical generator system [7].

Gallium-68 can be produced from the cyclotron through different reactions using various particles, such as protons, alpha and deuterons. Table 1. The most common method to produce Gallium-68 (^{68}Ga) involves the irradiation of enriched zinc-68 (^{68}Zn) with protons via the reaction $^{68}\text{Zn}(p:n)^{68}\text{Ga}$. This approach is highly efficient and widely used for clinical and research applications.[8] This approach is not only highly efficient but also offers significantly higher production yields compared to generator-based methods. The cross-section value for the $^{68}\text{Zn}(p:n)^{68}\text{Ga}$ reaction is shown in Fig-2 and the corresponding physical yield is also provided.

Table 1. production routes Ga 68 usng the cyclotron

Reaction	Energy rage MeV	Q-value MeV	Threshold MeV
$^{68}\text{Zn}(p:n)^{68}\text{Ga}$	3-14	-3.7	3.7
$^{65}\text{Cu}(a:n)^{68}\text{Ga}$	4-27	-5.0	6.1
$^{68}\text{Zn}(d:n)^{68}\text{Ga}$	5-18	-5.9	6.1

Figure 2. Cross-section value of $^{68}\text{Zn}(p:n)^{68}\text{Ga}$ and physical Yield of ^{68}Ga .

Theranostic application

Theranostics combines diagnostic imaging and therapy and ^{68}Ga plays a pivotal role in this field. For example, ^{68}Ga -labeled tracers are used for tumor localization, while therapeutic isotopes such as Lutetium-177 (^{177}Lu) are employed for treatment. This diagnostic-therapeutic pairing, exemplified by the $^{68}\text{Ga}/^{177}\text{Lu}$ -PSMA and $^{68}\text{Ga}/^{177}\text{Lu}$ -DOTA-conjugates, allows for personalized treatment planning and improved patient outcomes. [9] ^{68}Ga -PSMA is used in prostate cancer diagnostics by targeting prostate-specific membrane antigens (PSMA), which are commonly found on prostate cancer cells, enabling precise tumor imaging. ^{68}Ga -DOTA-conjugated peptides (e.g., DOTA-TATE, DOTA-TOC, DOTA-NOC) are used for imaging neuroendocrine tumors by binding to somatostatin receptors, which are overexpressed on tumor cells, providing accurate diagnostic information [10], shown in Fig-3.

Figure 3. Lutetium-177 Labelled PSMA Targeted Therapy

Conclusion

Gallium-68 (^{68}Ga) is a cornerstone in nuclear medicine, particularly for PET imaging and theranostic applications. Its favorable properties, such as a short half-life and efficient production methods, including both the $^{68}\text{Ge}/^{68}\text{Ga}$ generator and cyclotron-based techniques, make it a valuable tool in cancer diagnostics. ^{68}Ga 's ability to pair with therapeutic isotopes, such as ^{177}Lu , in theranostic approaches has revolutionized personalized treatment, allowing for more accurate tumor localization and targeted therapy. As ^{68}Ga -based radiopharmaceuticals continue to evolve, they are expected to significantly improve diagnostic precision and treatment outcomes for various cancers.

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